

ARCHITECTING THE OPENSEARCH SERVICE AT CERN FOR OPENWEBSEARCH.EU*

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Abstract

The Open Web Search.eu (OWS) project [1], aims to harness the untapped potential of the Web as a data source and make it accessible by developing a publicly funded, scalable and open European *Web search and analysis infrastructure* [2]. This research initiative is a joint venture that involves 14 research institutions throughout Europe [3], with CERN serving as one of the key technical infrastructure partners. The mission includes a robust, highly available continuous crawling operation, adhering to fundamental principles of openness and legal compliance. To this end, the OWS team has created the Open Web Crawler (OWLER) [4], an open-source software framework that facilitates the extensive collection of Web documents [5].

Amongst other, the OWLER comprises the *URL Frontier Service* which has the data structure containing all URLs discovered during the crawling process, effectively acting as the project's brain. It uses OpenSearch [6] technology as its primary back-end chosen for its robust persistence, distribution, and replication capabilities along with its indexing and querying capabilities, many of its open source plugins, and to leverage an existing OpenSearch-based implementation [7] of the open source URLFrontier framework [8] – which has been funded by NGI Zero [9].

The OpenSearch service is continuously operational at the CERN data center, and this article details along with our experience, its technical setup and evolution throughout different phases of the project, including the design, implementation, improvements made and the challenges we overcame. This has culminated in us effectively parsing, indexing, and storing ~7TiB of data at the time of writing this article. We also discuss the future roadmap before concluding the paper.

INTRODUCTION

The computational, data storage, and transfer tasks for the OWS project are executed within a distributed, heterogeneous infrastructure that spans five partner data center sites in Europe, including CERN. These data centers collectively manage a federated data infrastructure that leverages the confluence of HPC and cloud infrastructure [10], ensuring timely data availability for each step of the crawling, pre-processing, and indexing pipeline to collaboratively build a comprehensive web index. [11]. Given the capabilities of the computing and storage resources procured for the

OWS project at CERN and their alignment with project requirements, CERN was strategically chosen to establish the following services:

- *URL Frontier Service*: This is the core of the OWLER Web crawling system, comprising the data processing back-end and the Java front-end service applications.
- *Logs Aggregation and Monitoring Service*: Encompasses the data processing back-end and stream processing using Apache Flink [12] as illustrated in Figure 1, chosen for its robust real-time data processing capabilities and scalability.
- *Federated Data Storage and Transfer Management Service*: Manages data storage and transfer across distributed infrastructure [13] using iRODS [14] and MinIO [15] as illustrated in Figure 1.

OpenSearch serves as the data processing back-end for the first two services listed. In this paper, we will concentrate on the OpenSearch service, specifically in context to the URL Frontier Service, as the use case, since the same principles are applicable to the second service.

Data visualization and analysis, observability, and monitoring are implemented for the first two listed services using appropriate tools such as OpenSearch Dashboards [16], Prometheus [17], and Grafana [18].

From the initial phase of the project, at CERN we implemented a streamlined infrastructure set-up to achieve the milestone of developing a pilot version as outlined in the referenced deliverable [19]. This setup involved the manual deployment of vertically scaled and distributed OpenSearch clusters on bare metal machines whose specifications are detailed in a further section. This initial configuration consisted of two production clusters indexing approximately ~5 TiB of URL data totaling approximately 9.8 billion documents and 2.3 TiB of logs and metrics data as of March 2024, respectively, and has one test cluster.

As the main back-end for search, data ingestion, and log and metric aggregation in the OWLER system, this set-up initially fulfilled our requirements. However, as other components of OWLER expanded, it became clear that our infrastructure could not scale efficiently with the limited manpower available for interventions. This realization led to the investigation and evaluation of alternative methods for scalable and more manageable service and server management and maintenance approaches to support the growing needs and future expansion of the OWLER system.

The OpenSearch As-A-Service infrastructure at CERN IT, which provides a managed OpenSearch service for a wide

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Figure 1: OWS Infrastructure at CERN

range of CERN-based use cases, served as an invaluable reference for our objectives [20]. However, their reliance on Puppet for configuration management presented certain difficulties. In light of OWS’s dedication to open source values, we identified that a containerized infrastructure using tools like Podman [21] would offer considerable benefits over a Puppet-based setup. This method delivers a more user-friendly, scalable and portable solution that accommodates various experimental goals within the OWS and fulfills the expected integration needs of third parties [22]. Furthermore, this containerized configuration eases management for

the OWS team at CERN by minimizing manual interventions, resulting in minimal downtimes and ensuring reliability.

The initial section covers the architecture of the URL Frontier service and its interoperability with other services as depicted in Figure 1. The following section elaborates on the design of the OpenSearch service. The subsequent section provides an introduction to the new containerized infrastructure. This is followed by a section that outlines the roadmap, and finally, the remaining section offers a summary.

THE URL FRONTIER SERVICE

This section provides a brief overview of the design and functionalities of the URL Frontier Service operational at CERN. It leverages the OpenSearch Service as its backend, which we will discuss in detail in the upcoming section.

By implementing the URL Frontier as a "service", we can handle it as an independent functional unit deployable and manageable across a network. This approach is designed for reusability, scalability, modularity, and interoperability within the broader service-oriented architecture of OWS's federated data infrastructure [19]. Interoperability allows seamless integration and communication with other services, enhancing system efficiency and flexibility. In addition, this design decision ensures effective management, high performance, and reliability, facilitating easier maintenance and updates without disrupting the entire system.

The URL Frontier Service, part of the OWLer Web crawling system, tracks the status of discovered and uncrawled URLs. Crawlers continuously fetch web pages from the public Web and retrieve URLs through remote calls to the URL Frontier service. After crawling, the URLs and discovered outlinks are uploaded back to the URL Frontier service, which updates the crawl status. Each crawling node interacts solely with the URL Frontier service to retrieve and upload web links.

The URL Frontier Service can consist of multiple Java front-end service applications, each connected to one or more crawler services, and an OpenSearch service acting as a back-end.

Figure 1 shows the configuration of the distributed OWS infrastructure of CERN. Two Java front-end service applications operate on distinct machines (`ows-frontier2.cern.ch` and `ows-frontier3.cern.ch` as shown in Figure 1), with the OpenSearch cluster distributed across these and two additional machines (`ows-frontier.cern.ch` and `ows-test.cern.ch` in Figure 1). The crawlers, hosted in other data centers (OWS Partner Data Center 1-3 in Figure 1), connect to the URL Frontier Service. The two Java Service Applications interact with these peer-to-peer crawling nodes in the partner data centers via the URLFrontier API [23] and connect to the OpenSearch cluster¹ via the OpenSearch Java high-level REST client [24]. It also connects to the OpenSearch cluster in the *Logs Aggregation and Monitoring Service*, which is on another machine (`ows-metrics.cern.ch` in Figure 1) This setup allows for various operations on the OpenSearch cluster, including indexing, searching, data management, logs, and metrics aggregation.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the above-mentioned services along with the other interface services [25]. OpenSearch Dashboards are utilized for data visualization and analysis due to their powerful and flexible tools that integrate seamlessly with OpenSearch. Smooth data processing and collection require all computing and storage systems to be fully operational and available. To continuously monitor and ensure the health and performance of these systems,

we integrated Grafana for monitoring and Prometheus for observability. Grafana provides real-time visualization and dashboards, while Prometheus handles data collection in time series format and alerting. All the mentioned services are currently not accessible from outside the participating services that connect from the partner data center hosts, whose IPs are secured. To ensure encrypted communication between different services, we use SSL certificates from a highly trusted authority.

OPENSEARCH SERVICE DESIGN

This section provides an overview of the main subject of this paper. The architecture of the OpenSearch service is presented in detail, including the robust hardware infrastructure on which it operates. The figure also covers both legacy and modern deployment strategies; next we touch briefly on the dedicated test environment setup followed by authentication and authorization processes, and the various security measures implemented. In addition, it highlights the observability and monitoring mechanisms as well as the business continuity and disaster recovery strategies used. Figure 2 offers an illustration of the architecture, which is based on the more detailed design depicted in Figure 1. This figure maintains the representation of the data flow within the distributed setup of the service.

A significant aspect of this architecture is its utilization of CERN's two data center regions, as depicted in Figure 2 to ensure high availability and disaster recovery. By leveraging these geographically separated data centers, the service can maintain operational continuity even in the event of a failure in one region. This is achieved through a dedicated cluster approach, which minimizes external dependencies and enhances the flexibility and adaptability of the service. This approach not only supports the current use cases but is also designed to accommodate future requirements. The dedicated cluster setup ensures that the two services using OpenSearch as their data processing back-end can operate efficiently and reliably.

Hardware Specification

The OpenSearch service at CERN is currently deployed on five physical machines within a single availability zone as depicted in Figure 2. Initially they ran CentOS Stream 8, later we had to migrate to Alma Linux 8 based on the advice of the CERN IT Linux Committee. [26] Each machine features 64 CPU cores, 256 GB of RAM, and 10.5 TB of usable allocated SSD space. These machines are managed by OpenStack [27] ironic [28] without a virtualization layer. Configuration management is centralized using Puppet [29], with configuration data stored in GitLab at CERN [30].

Deployment Strategy

Our existing two production clusters demand significant resources, hence they are each set up on dedicated machines. The adaptable nature of the configuration allows resource adjustments according to specific requirements. Logical

¹ Cluster: An independent OpenSearch cluster, dedicated to one use case.

Figure 2: OpenSearch Service at CERN for OWS

Volume Manager (LVM) offers an abstraction layer over the physical storage available, facilitating the creation of Logical Volumes (LVs) that can extend across several physical disks. This allows dynamic volume resizing, backup snapshots, and the integration of new storage devices without requiring downtime. By efficiently managing storage across physical disks, LVs enable easy expansion as clusters near their capacity.

Due to the growing demand for additional data nodes², particularly for the URL Frontier Service, we incorporated data nodes (which also manage Search and Ingest roles) on two additional machines and one test machine, as depicted in Figure 2. These nodes are configured to connect to the original cluster manager node, which is different from the data node on the same machine. For greater storage needs, each cluster has the capability to connect to the external S3 storage cluster. In our infrastructure, a data node from each of the clusters handling Search and Ingest roles, similar to the production data nodes, is strategically placed on the test machine.

Dedicated test environment

The test machine ‘ows-test.cern.ch’ shown in Figure 2 is set up to closely replicate the production environment. This setup includes similar hardware and software configurations. It features a dedicated test cluster and also hosts test data nodes from the other two production clusters. New integra-

tions and third-party services are initially tested on these nodes to ensure they work seamlessly with the production clusters and later on rolled out to production nodes. This setup also allows the validation of software updates, configuration changes, and new features before they are deployed in the production environment. This step is crucial to ensure compatibility and identify any potential problems, e.g. to identify breaking changes. By isolating the test environment, we can perform extensive tests without jeopardizing the stability and performance of the production clusters.

Authentication and Authorization

The authentication is handled by OpenSearch, which maintains an internal database of user roles and encrypted passwords. Authorization is carried out within OpenSearch, incorporating CERN LDAP to manage access based on CERN e-groups.

Security

Let’s Encrypt [31] fulfills our criteria for a highly reliable certificate authority by offering SSL certificates via an automated procedure to secure communications between services. We follow the official OpenSearch documentation for configuring security. Since Let’s Encrypt issues certificates in PEM format, which are incompatible with OpenSearch’s required PKCS12 formats, we use the OpenSSL [32] tool for conversion. By setting up OpenSearch with these SSL certificates, all communications between the nodes, between the clusters, and other services are encrypted, ensuring data

² An instance of the OpenSearch process

security and integrity. Let's Encrypt certificates have a typical validity of 90 days. Using Certbot [33] we renew these certificates periodically and update the service(s) configuration as needed.

Resource Monitoring and Performance Evaluation

The system utilizes Node Exporter [34] to collect resource indicator data, such as CPU usage, memory usage, and system load, and exports these data to the dedicated port. Prometheus, a powerful monitoring and alerting toolkit, collects these metrics from Node Exporter and stores them as time series data. The time series data allow Prometheus to efficiently store and query metrics over time, providing a historical view of system performance.

Grafana, a visualization tool, is deployed on the same machines to provide a user-friendly interface for real-time monitoring. Grafana connects to Prometheus to fetch the stored metrics and offers customizable dashboards that display various resource indicators. This setup allows us to gain insight into system performance, identify trends, and quickly troubleshoot issues.

In addition, the Prometheus Exporter Plug-In [35] for OpenSearch is used to expose cluster metrics in a format compatible with Prometheus. This plug-in collects key metrics such as cluster status, node status, and index status from the clusters via its REST API. By integrating these metrics into Prometheus and visualizing them in Grafana, we monitor the health and performance of the clusters alongside other system metrics.

Business Continuity and Disaster recovery

We regularly take snapshots to backup the cluster's indexes and state. These snapshots are stored in an S3 cluster (s3.cern.ch/ows in Figure 1) in a different CERN data center region (CERN Region 2 in Figure 2), while our OpenSearch clusters are in another region (CERN Region 1 in Figure 2). This setup improves reliability, uptime, data integrity, and availability. In case of cluster failures, such as red health status, hardware issues, data corruption, or accidental deletions, snapshots have allowed us to restore indexes, minimizing downtime and data loss. We were able to quickly restore the unavailable or corrupted indexes from the latest snapshot to resume normal operations. Each of our clusters uses individual S3 buckets specified in the snapshot repository settings. We have a snapshot schedule for regular backups, semi-automated via the OpenSearch Dashboards Developer Tools, ensuring consistent snapshot creation by executing a query.

Migrating to containerized deployments

To package and deploy the service along with its dependencies in isolated environments for open-source distribution and to manage a horizontally scalable multi-node OpenSearch cluster, we have transitioned to a multi-container infrastructure solution using Podman. Containers are lightweight, portable, and consistent in various environments, making them perfect for deployment and scaling.

Using OpenSearch containers in this way allows us to have fine-grained control over the routing of incoming connections to the various other services that we are running. We were able to perform updates in production without service outages. When a third-party user decides to use our open-source distribution of the URL Frontier service, by making use of container limits, they should be able to deploy the services on low-end hardware without significant needs for intervention.

The firewall settings are adapted so that all machines can communicate with each other for each use case. Live data was started to be ingested as a test on one of the newly containerized cluster. The implementation process had near-zero downtime and allowed ample time for testing and verification.

LVs are mounted as persistent storage volumes within the containers. This setup ensures that data persists across container restarts and deployments. Containers are configured to use these mounted volumes for storing data, index templates, retention policies, and OpenSearch Dashboards objects.

FUTURE WORK

Despite having a limited number of dedicated personnel, there are numerous opportunities to further investigate and improve the service. This section discusses some of the proposed ideas. To support service management and operations, the plan includes further developing and expanding the Puppet repository to automate various operational tasks. The host machines will transition from AlmaLinux 8 to AlmaLinux 9, following the recommendations of the CERN Linux Committee. Secrets management will be handled through Teigi [36]. OpenSearch's snapshot lifecycle management (SLM) feature will be utilized to ensure that snapshots are created consistently and without manual intervention with a fixed schedule. Furthermore, with the implementation of scalable multinode containerized infrastructure, we will also scale up our monitoring and logging infrastructure to a centralized system. This will allow us to aggregate logs from all OpenSearch nodes to a single location for easier management and analysis. Advanced alert mechanisms will be implemented using Prometheus to scrape additional metrics to monitor resource usage and trigger alerts when thresholds are exceeded, thus optimizing resource utilization and performance. Since May 20, 2023, CERN has been recognized as an official OpenSearch partner. The aim is to enhance CERN's visibility within the OpenSearch community and actively participate in meetings and forums to contribute to the community's development and growth.

CONCLUSION

This paper provided an in-depth exploration of the successful implementation and operation process of the OpenSearch service at CERN for the OWS project. Motivated by maintainability, open source licensing, and improved features availability, the implementation aimed to overcome chal-

allenges faced in the pilot version and leverage containerisations' capabilities. The new service architecture adopts a new improved deployment strategy with multiple nodes and clusters hosted on powerful machines, ensuring resource efficiency. The paper concludes with a roadmap for further automation, community engagement, and exploration of OpenSearch capabilities. In general, it provides a comprehensive and informative account of the implementation journey, making it a valuable resource for research projects considering or undergoing similar transitions.

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